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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE INTRAVENOUS OCTEROTIDE
EFFICACY IN EARLY VARICEAL REBLEED PREVENTION
AFTER SCLEROTHERAPY****¹Dr. Muhammad Tanveer Sajid, ²Dr. Abdul Farooq, ³Dr. Maria Khalid**¹Latin American School of Medicine, Cuba²FMH College of Medicine and Dentistry, Lahore³Nishtar Medical University, Multan**Abstract:**

Objective: To evaluate the efficacy of intravenous octreotide after sclerotherapy in the prevention of early variceal bleeding.

Study Design: A descriptive study of the case series.

Place and Duration: In the Medical Unit II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from August 2017 to August 2018.

Methods: The study included 200 patients with variceal bleeding. All patients received 50 µg of octreotide bolus followed by continuous intravenous infusion of 50 / g / hour and sclerotherapy 12-24 hours later. After sclerotherapy, these 200 cases were continued with intravenous octreotide at 50 µg / hr for 48 hours. All patients were observed for early bleeding findings within 5 days with a history of hematemesis and melena.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 41,3 + 9.8. There were 30 (15%) patients, first degree, 78 (39%) patients, second degree and 92 (46%) patients with variceal bleeding. Of the patients, 135 (67.5%) had ascites, and 65 (32.5%) didn't. Hematemesis and melena were present in the distribution of new patients (14%) and in 172 (86%) of them there was no hematemesis / melena.

Conclusion: Intravenous octreotide is an effective treatment method to prevent bleeding within 5 days after sclerotherapy in cirrhotic patients.

Key words: hepatic cirrhosis, esophageal varices, sclerotherapy, octreotide.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cirrhosis is a very common disease in our country due to infection caused by hepatitis B and C. portal hypertension producing spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, ascites, variceal bleeding and hepatic encephalopathy. The cirrhosis most common cause in 47% is Chronic hepatitis C, followed by chronic hepatitis B in 32%. Hepatitis B and C are present in 3% of the patients. Approximately 84.6% of patients with cirrhosis and portal hypertension develop gastroesophageal varices, but only one-third have severe bleeding. If left untreated, the time of hospitalization is increased. The mortality rate is 30% within two weeks after the acute bleeding event. Acute variceal bleeding is an emergency in Pakistan with high risk of bleeding and mortality. Early endoscopy is necessary to confirm the diagnosis and also to perform therapeutic procedures such as sclerotherapy and bands. This can be combined with treatment with I / V drugs such as octreotide. Treatment options for acute attack include octreotide, terlipressin, balloon tamponade, endoscopic emergency band and sclerotherapy. Without further treatment, there is a risk of 60-80% bleeding during 2 years and a 50% bleeding risk within 7 days. For the prevention of new bleedings, sclerotherapy, bands, beta blockers, nitrates and Tran's intra-jugular Porto systemic shunt (TIPS) are used. Early variceal hemorrhage is a problem within 10 days after sclerotherapy. If octreotide is used for 48 hours after sclerotherapy, it can be discussed today if it prevents early bleeding. The purpose of this analysis was to evaluate the intravenous octreotide efficacy in the prevention of early hemorrhage after sclerotherapy and thus to adopt a better treatment strategy. A general impression based on the hemodynamic state

at the end of the study showed that the patient was clinically more stable and received an octreotide infusion after sclerotherapy by injection and a decrease in bleeding after sclerotherapy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It was a descriptive study of the case series held in the Medical Unit II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from August 2017 to August 2018. The study included 200 cirrhosis patients, aged between 20 and 60 years, who were confirmed by abdominal ultrasound, male / female and with gastroscopy-confirmed esophageal varices. The patients were asked about the confounding variables, hemoglobin level, the degree of varices and the presence of ascites. After sclerotherapy, all patients were given 50 µg of octreotide bolus. After 12-24 hours, these 200 cases continued with intravenous octreotide at 50 µg / hr for 48 hours. All patients were given all other standard drugs with antibiotics, lactulose and proton pump inhibitors. All patients were observed in terms of varices findings within a period of 05 days, that is, a history of hematemesis and malena; He also had new bleeding symptoms. Using SPSS version 17.0, the data was analyzed.

RESULTS:

200 total patients who met the inclusion criteria of acute upper gastrointestinal bleeding due to changes in medical emergency were included in the study. 41.3 ± 9.8 years was the mean age of the patients. There were 33 (16.5%) patients in the 21-30 age group, 60 (30%) patients in the 31-40 age group, and 63 (31.5%) patients in the 41-50 age range and 44 (22%) patients were between 51 and 60 years (Table 1).

Table 1: distribution by age (n=200)

Age (years)	=n	%age
21-30	33	16.5
31-40	60	30
41-50	63	31.5
51-60	44	22

Mean±SD: 41.9±9.8

SD standard deviation

There were 75 (37.5%) female and 125 (62.5%) male patients patients in the gender distribution (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution by sex (n=200)

Sex	=n	%age
Male	125	62.5
Female	75	37.5

In hemoglobin levels, 137 (68.5%) patients had less than 10 mg / dl hemoglobin level and 63 patients (31.5%) had more than 10 mg / dl. In the distribution of varices, there were grade I (15%) patients, grade II (39%) patients, and Grade III (3%) 92 (46%) patients with varices (Table 3).

Table 3: Distribution by grades of varices (n=200)

Sex	=n	%age
Grade I	30	15
Grade II	78	39
Grade III	92	46

Ascites was present in 135 patients (67.5%) and was not present in 65 patients (32.5%) (Table 4).

Table 4: Distribution by ascites (n=200)

Ascites	=n	%age
Yes	135	67.5
No	65	32.5

Hematemesis evidence / new bleeding was present in 28 (14%) patients and was not present in 172 (86%) patients (Table 5).

Table 5: Distribution by evidence of re bleed (n=200)

Hematemesis/ malena	=n	%age
Yes	58	14
No	172	86

DISCUSSION:

Liver cirrhosis is a common disease in our country due to hepatitis B and C infection. Gastroesophageal varices occur in approximately 84.6% of patients with cirrhosis and portal hypertension, but one third of them have severe variceal bleeding. If left untreated, half of the time of hospitalization is repeated. The mortality rate is 30% within 2 weeks after the acute bleeding event. For acute octreotide section, balloon tamponade, emergency endoscopic dressing and sclerotherapy are the treatment options. There is a risk of bleeding between 60 - 80% for 2 years without an additional treatment and there is a 50% risk of bleeding within 10 days. Re-bleeding is a problem within 5 days after early injection

sclerotherapy. If octreotide is used for 48 hours after sclerotherapy, it can be discussed today if it prevents early bleeding. In one study, efficacy of octreotide with sclerotherapy alone (50 isg / hour for 48 hours) was compared with sclerotherapy alone in patients with acute bleeding of esophageal varices. The primary outcome of the study was 5-day survival without re-bleeding. In 90.2% of patients receiving combined therapy, bleeding control was only 75.9% of patients in the sclerotherapy group. In our study, the mean age of the patients was 41.3 ± 9.8 years according to Farooqi studies. In our study, according to Farooqi studies, 62.5% were male and 37.5% were female. In our study, the varices were of stage I in 39%, stage II, 39%, and 46% of stage III. According

to Farooqi studies 20. 42% of patients with grade I who could be compared with our study. In our study, 14% of patients had hematemesis / malena in a new evidence of bleeding, and 86% of patients had no new evidence of bleeding compared to the study by Muhammad and Rub. The overall bleeding was 10% of the patients. We studied 157 consecutive cases who underwent immediate sclerotherapy due to acute variceal bleeding, followed by a continuous octreotide infusion (25 µg) comparable to our study. According to Besson et al 199 patients in double-blind prospective studies, with acute variceal bleeding under emergency sclerotherapy were given randomly continuous octreotide (25 µg / hr) or for 5 days given placebo infusion. After 5 days, the rate of survivors without repeat bleeding was higher in the octreotide group and in the octreotide group (p = 0.006) the need for blood transfusion was lower.

CONCLUSION:

Intravenous octreotide is an effective treatment for the prevention of early bleeding after sclerotherapy within five days in cirrhotic patients.

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